

Assess the effectiveness of information booklet on knowledge about asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers visiting antenatal clinics of various hospitals.

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ABSTRACT

Asymptomatic bacteriuria is the presence of bacteria in the properly collected urine of a patient that has no signs or symptoms of a urinary tract infection. Asymptomatic bacteriuria is the presence of bacteria in the properly collected urine of a patient that has no signs or symptoms of a urinary tract infection and is found in 2 to 15% of pregnant women during 1st trimester of the clinic. Up to 30% of mothers have experienced acute pyelonephritis if untreated. Asymptomatic bacteriuria has been linked to preterm birth and low birth weight and it is linked to severe maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, it is important to obstetricians. Thirty percent of them might later develop an acute symptomatic infection while pregnancy and causative organisms are predisposing factors for asymptomatic bacteriuria poverty and lack of sanitation. Asymptomatic bacteriuria, which affects 2% to 15% of pregnancies, is a bacterial infection of the urine without any of the typical symptoms of a urinary infection. Up to 27% of women will experience acute pyelonephritis if untreated. Asymptomatic bacteriuria has been linked to preterm birth and low birth weight.

For this study **Quantitative research approach** with research design adopted for the present study was pre-experimental one-group pre-test post-test research design. **60 samples** were taken through non-probability convenient sampling techniques.

RESULT: 43.3% of the first trimester mothers were age 18-24 years, and 56.7% of them had age 25-31 years. 45% of them had joint families and 55% of them had nuclear families. 56.7% of them had higher education and 43.3% of them had secondary education. 60% of them were

housewives and 40% of them had service. 35% of them had a family income of Rs. 20000-30000, 51.7% of them had a family income of Rs. 40000-50000 and 13.3% of them had a family income of Rs. 60000-70000. 75% of the first-trimester mothers had average knowledge (score 7-13) and 25% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management. The average knowledge score in the pretest was 12.4 which increased to 16.3 in the post test. The t-value for this test was 14.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The knowledge among first-trimester mothers improved significantly after the information booklet regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management.

INTRODUCTION-

Asymptomatic bacteriuria is the presence of bacteria in the properly collected urine of a patient that has no signs or symptoms of a urinary tract infection and is found in 2 to 15% of pregnant women during 1st trimester of the clinic. Up to 30% of mothers have experienced acute pyelonephritis if untreated. Asymptomatic bacteriuria has been linked to preterm birth and low birth weight and it is linked to severe maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, it is important to obstetricians. Thirty percent of them might later develop an acute symptomatic infection while pregnancy and causative organisms are predisposing factors for asymptomatic bacteriuria poverty and lack of sanitation. Asymptomatic bacteriuria, which affects 2% to 15% of pregnancies, is a bacterial infection of the urine without any of the typical symptoms of a urinary infection. Up to 27% of women will experience acute pyelonephritis if untreated.

NEED OF STUDY

This study aimed to determine the prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria, the isolated bacterial agents, and their antibiotic sensitivity patterns in pregnant women attending antenatal care. Screening for asymptomatic bacteriuria is a standard of obstetrical care and is included in most antenatal guidelines. There is good evidence that treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria will decrease the incidence of pyelonephritis. All pregnant women are screened for asymptomatic bacteriuria, and there are no new data that would indicate otherwise. Antibiotic treatment of asymptomatic bacteriuria is associated with a decrease in the incidence of preterm delivery or low birth weight, but the methodological quality of the studies means any conclusion about the strength of this association needs to be drawn cautiously.

METHODOLOGY

A research design is an investigative plan, structure, and technique developed to find answers to research questions or problems. The research plan is the entire research program. It outlines everything the investigator will perform, from developing the hypothesis through its operational implications to the final data analysis. The backbone or structure of the study is the research design. The word research design refers to a scientific investigation's plan or organization. It provides a framework that supports and integrates the research. The research design aids the researcher in the subject selection, **one group pre-test post-test experimental design**, data collection process, and statistical analysis type to be utilized to interpret the findings. The research design adopted for the present study was **pre-experimental one-group pretest post-test research design**.

ANALYSIS

SECTION I:

Description of Socio-demographic data of the visiting antenatal clinics of various hospitals.

Age:

According to age 43.3% of the first trimester mothers were age they had 18-24 years, and 56.7% of them had age 25-31 years. Type of family: According to type of family 45% of first trimester mothers they had joint families and 55% of them had nuclear families.

Education:

According to education 56.7% of them had higher education and 43.3% of them had secondary education

Occupation:

According to occupation 60% of them were housewives and 40% of them had service.

Income of family: According to income of family 35% of them had a family income of Rs. 20000-30000, 51.7% of them had a family income of Rs. 40000-50000 and 13.3% of them had a family income of Rs. 60000-70000.

SECTION-II

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of the information booklet on asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first-trimester mothers

In the pretest, 75% of the first-trimester mothers had average knowledge (score 7-13) and 25% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management. In the post-test, all the first-trimester mothers had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management. This indicates that the knowledge regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first-trimester mothers improved remarkably after the information booklet.

SECTION – III

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of information booklet on asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers

Table 3: Effectiveness of information booklet on asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers In pretest, 75% of the first trimester mothers had average knowledge (score 7-13) and 25% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management. In posttest, all the first trimester mothers had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management. This indicates that the knowledge regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers improved remarkably after the information booklet.

SECTION IV

Paired t-test for the effectiveness of information booklet on asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first-trimester mothers. The research applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of an information booklet on asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first-trimester mothers. The average knowledge score in the pretest was 12.4 which increased to 16.3 in the posttest. The t-value for this test was 14.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The knowledge among first-trimester mothers improved significantly after the information booklet regarding asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management.

ITEM ANALYSIS

CONCLUSION:

This chapter has dealt with the analysis and interpretation findings of the study and conclusion. Both descriptive and inferential statistics have been used to analyse the data. The data analysis and interpretation are described based on research objectives.

DELIMITATION:

The research is delimited to among first trimester mothers visiting antenatal clinics of various hospitals. The data collection period was limited to 7 days after the implication of intervention.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations. A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized. The study can be replicated in different settings. The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study. Other interventions rather than a knowledge questionnaire can also be used in the study. An experimental study can be performed using different types of interventions. A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples. A study may be conducted to evaluate the 'Assess the effectiveness of information

booklet on knowledge about asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers visiting antenatal clinics of various hospitals.’

SUMMARY

This chapter dealt with major findings implications, delimitations, recommendations, and conclusions of the ‘Assess the effectiveness of information booklet on knowledge about asymptomatic bacteriuria and its management among first trimester mothers visiting antenatal clinics of various hospitals.’

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